

CONSUMER DISPOSITION TOWARDS MANGROVE OYSTER (*Crassostrea gasar*)
CONSUMPTION IN SELECTED FISHING COMMUNITIES OF RIVERS STATE, NIGERIA

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ABSTRACT

The edible mangrove oyster *Crassostrea gasar* is a delicacy in many communities of Rivers State. The consumer disposition and perception towards oyster consumption were determined in selected fishing communities of the state. 200 structured questionnaires were randomly distributed in 10 communities (20 per community) across three local government areas. The results from the study indicated that oyster consumption was more acceptable among the old people than the younger ones. A greater number of people 95.5% considered oysters as fish, 2.0% as pest, 1.0% as nuisance and 1.5% were indifferent. Also, 80.5% of the respondents were favourably disposed towards oyster consumption, 13.5% were negative and 6.09% were indifferent. The study revealed that there is no taboo in the consumption of oyster in these communities, any disposition and perception observed during the study was personal to individual and not the affair of the community.

KEYWORDS: Oyster, disposition, consumer, perception, Niger delta

INTRODUCTION

The mangrove oyster inhabits the mangrove swampland of the Niger delta. It is available in the natural waters and thrives well in water with 10-25 part per thousand salinity and temperature range of 23 – 31^oc (Ansa and Bashir, 2007). In most parts of Niger Delta oyster can be sourced from the wild and it can also be cultured in brackish mangrove swamps. Ajana (1979) reported that sheltered areas with a water depth ranging from 2 – 5m offering protection from strong waves and free from pollution are suitable sites for oyster culture.

Cultural practices, beliefs and perceptions have been known to influence the way foods are prepared, vendored and eaten by different populations, which affect the likelihood of people's perception to the food item (Bryan *et al.*, 1992; Murphy and Oliver, 1992; Bouchriti *et al.*, 1995). In Niger Delta oyster is a delicacy among the populace, where it is generally believed that it is a major source of protein, mineral and vitamins needed for daily growth (Akinrotimi *et al.*, 2005) while in some other parts of the world oyster consumption is perceived to be an harbinger of illness in the consumers. (Laloo *et al.*, 2000). This is based on the fact that mangrove swamps that serve as habitats for oysters are grossly polluted due to industrial, agricultural and oil explorative activities.

The consumer disposition toward oyster consumption in fishing communities of Niger Delta has not been studied empirically for ideal processing and packaging methods that will satisfy the need of consumer. Akinrotimi *et al.* (2010a) noted that disposition is an individual affair that varies from one person to another. Hence analysis of consumer disposition towards oyster consumption is urgent and crucial to satisfy consumer need and to enhance production process. There is also a dearth of information on the attitudes and individual perception of the populace about oyster consumption in the country. This study therefore analyzed some consumers' disposition and perception towards oyster consumption in some fishing communities of Rivers State.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Area of Study

The study was conducted in 10 communities; covering three local government areas Buguma, Ido, Abalama, Tema, Okpo and Ilelema (Asari Toru Local Government Area); Obuama and Degema (Degema Local Government Area), Abonnema and Obonoma (Akuku-Toru Local Government Area) all in Rivers State, Nigeria. These areas are surrounded by large water bodies, with evergreen tropical rainforest and mangrove swamps predominant in the area.

Sampling Procedure and Data Collection

The sample for the study was collected randomly from the stated 10 communities, 20 respondents were randomly selected in each town to give a total sample size of 200, this was done to allow easy retrieval of the questionnaires. Data for the study were generated through structure questionnaires administered in these areas. Data collected include socio-economic characteristics, such as sex, age, marital status, educational level, occupation and consumer perception, disposition and attitudes towards consumption of oysters.

Statistical Analysis

Descriptive statistics involving the use of measure of central tendency such as frequency, percentage and chart were used to analyze the data (Wahua, 1999).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The socio-economic characteristics of oyster consumers during the study are shown in Table 1. The data obtained indicated that the highest oyster consumer (29.0%) was observed in the age bracket 26 – 40 years closely followed (26.0%) by 41 – 60 years, while those in 10 – 15 years recorded the lowest (7.0%). This result indicated that oyster consumption was more acceptable among the old class than the young ones. This is in line with the report of Melane and Peterson (2005) in Chesapenke Bay, along the mid Atlantic coast of the USA, who observed that about 70% of oyster consumers were adult above 25 years of age, an indication that oyster is more acceptable among the old people as compared to school children, teenagers and young people. Out of the consumers analyzed, 52.0% were male, while 48.0% were females. The marital status revealed that majority (54.0%) of the oyster consumers were single, and the widows/widowers were in the minority (20%). Occupationally, the distribution indicated that fishermen had the highest percentage (20.5%), while the retirees and craftsmen had the lowest (7.0%). These results agree with the finding of Laloo *et al.*, (2000) in coastal areas of Trinidad and Tobago, who reported that most of the oyster consumers were old people, male dominated and majority were fishermen. The fact that consumption of oysters is associated with more of male and with being aged 40 and above may have some health implications such as increased libido (Hlady and Klontz, 1996).

The perception of oyster by the respondents indicated that 95.5% considered oyster as shell fish, 2.0% considered it as a pest, 1.0% perceived it to be nuisance and 1.5% were indifferent (Table 2). The various perceptions about oyster recorded during this study in various communities, disagree with the findings of House *et al.* (2003) in the eastern North Carolina in the United States. The difference observed may be due to level of awareness among the people in these areas, as Akinrotimi *et al.* (2010b) observed that awareness level determines perception of food item in a community.

The general disposition towards oyster is highly favourable (80.5%), 13.5% were in the negative, while 6.0% were indifferent (Table 3). This results may be due to the fact that oyster is popular and acceptable among the older generation who are more in number in rural communities (Akinrotimi *et al.*, 2007). The consumption trend of oyster among the respondents revealed that 95.0% consume oyster, 3.5% do not consume and 1.5% were indifferent (Table 4). Interestingly oyster consumption pattern is very high among the respondents an indication that oyster is very common and popular in the coastal areas of Niger delta (Deekae *et al.*, 1994; Ansa and Ansa, 2004). The consumer preference of oyster to fin fish were analyzed, 69.0% prefer fish while 23.0% prefer oyster and 8.0% prefer both on equal basis. The reason why more people have preference for fish in the study area may be as a result of the fact that fish is readily available in communities more than oyster, while those that prefer oyster to fish gave reason that oyster is more tasty and nutritious compared to fish.

The distribution of respondent on the way oyster is being utilized in the communities is shown in figure 1, 7.3% believed it is used as condiment, 20% as meat and 7% as sex stimulant. On safe consumption of oyster products 87% of the respondents believe it is safe, 10% indicated it is not safe, while 3% of the respondents are not sure. (Figure 2) This result contradicts that of Bouchriti (1995) in Moroccan islands and Laloo (2000) in the coastal areas of Trinidad and Tobago. The contradiction may be due to the fact that, oyster are normally processed and prepared before eaten in most Niger delta communities unlike in Moroccan Island and Trinidad and Tobago, where they are consumed raw. The fact that raw oysters are rarely subjected to any heat treatment before consumption, when sold by vendors in Trinidad increases the health risk where most people considered it not being safe. However, heated and well prepared oyster are rarely implicated in any diseases outbreak in Niger delta.

CONCLUSION

This study on Consumer disposition and perception of oysters consumption in some fishing communities of Rivers State, Nigeria is an attempt to identify some perceptions and disposition of people about consumption of mangrove oyster in these areas. This study should also be conducted in other communities in the region with the objective to fully assess comprehensively the perception and disposition of oyster consumption. It is only when consumer interests are adequately assessed that aquaculture can be fully developed to meet the need of people aquatic products in the coastal communities. This will ultimately result in increased production for sustainability of aquaculture industry in Niger delta.

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Table 1: Distribution of Socio-Economic Characteristics of Respondent (n=200)

Socio-economic variable	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Age (year)		
10 – 15	14	7.0
16 – 25	46	23.0
26 – 40	58	29.0
41 – 60	52	26.0
Above 60	29	14.5
Total	200	100
Gender		
Male	106	52
Female	94	48
Total	200	100
Marital Status		
Single	108	54
Married	82	41
Divorced	6	3
Widow	4	2
Total	200	100
Number in the Household		
1 – 4	82	41.0
5 – 10	96	48.0
Above 10	22	11.0
Total	200	100
Educational Status		
Primary	30	15.0
Secondary	42	21.0
Tertiary	42	21.0
None	18	9.0
Total	200	100
Occupation		
Businessman	23	11.5
Student	35	17.5
Fisherman	41	20.5
Craftsmen	14	7.0
Civil servant	18	9.0
Petty trader	25	12.5
Applicant	14	7.0
Housewife	16	8.0
Retirees	14	7.0
Total	200	100

Table 2: Perception of Respondents toward oyster (n=200)

Variable	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Shell fish	191	95.5
Pest	4	2.0
Nuisance	2	1.0
Indifferent	3	1.5
Total	200	100

Table 3: Respondents Disposition towards oyster (n=200)

Variable	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Favourable (positive)	161	80.5
Unfavourable (negative)	27	13.5
Indifferent	12	6.0
Total	200	100

Table 4: Distribution of Respondents by Consumption of oyster (n = 200)

Variable	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Consume oyster	190	95.0
Do not consume	7	3.5
Indifferent	3	1.5
Total	200	100

Table 5: Distribution of respondents preference of Mudskipper to fish (n = 200)

Variable	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Yes (Prefer oyster to fish)	46	23.0
No (prefer fish to oyster)	136	69.0
All (prefer both fish and oyster)	16	8.0
Total	200	100

Figure 1: Distribution of Respondent Utilization of Oyster

Figure 2: Respondent Response on the Safety of Oyster Consumption

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